

Organizing and Developing a Handball Game with Cadets and Students

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published online: 22 November 2021	This article discusses the organization of a handball team from cadets, listeners, pilots and engineers and the components of the handball system, its main tasks, developing the skills of cadets and listeners through the game of handball and instinct to make quick decisions. Information about the game is provided.
Corresponding Author: Bekhzod Kochkarovich Daminov	It is necessary for a serviceman of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan to be physically strong and to make non-standard decisions in non-standard situations. Therefore, it has become a topical issue for cadets and students to spend their free time meaningfully and to focus on sports that develop speed, endurance and willpower. Handball, which is one of these sports, is a way for cadets and listeners to work together as a team, to respect each other, to work for the team, to get out of situations during the game. It is no exaggeration to say that the combat situations you perform for your defense help you perform a variety of combat missions.
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INTRODUCTION

After the independence of Uzbekistan, the social mission of physical education was to improve the health of the people, their comprehensive development. The development of a healthy generation in Uzbekistan, the successful implementation of education, serves as one of the important social, economic and political tasks in the development of society.

It is necessary and necessary for a serviceman of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan to be physically strong and to make non-standard decisions in non-standard situations. Therefore, it has become a topical issue for cadets and students to spend their free time meaningfully and to focus on sports that develop speed, endurance and willpower. Handball, which is one of these sports, is a way for cadets and listeners to work together as a team, to respect each other, to work for the team, to get out of situations during the game. It is no exaggeration to say that the combat situations you perform for your defense help you perform a variety of combat missions. In particular, the purpose of handball sports and theory - educational-methodical, scientific-methodical work, implementation of spiritual-enlightenment processes and training and qualification of scientific-pedagogical specialists, handball methodology, handball tools, handball principles, training assists in the organization and conduct of games and competitions, training in handball techniques and tactics, means of increasing and developing physical fitness,

the basics of sports training, as well as the acquisition of practical and theoretical knowledge.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Scientific and methodological support is an integral part of the system of training handball players. Its main task is to develop practical recommendations in the following areas:

- forecasting achievements in sports;
- development of model descriptions;
- programming of competitions and training systems;
- carrying out restorative measures;
- improving the selection criteria;
- development of recommendations for the editing of training programs on the basis of comprehensive control.

Complex scientific groups of specialists on the basis of sports departments of higher military educational institutions, practical laboratories of the Scientific Research Institute of Physical Culture and Sports (CSG) for the organization of scientific and methodological support of national and club teams in higher military educational institutions, military higher educational institutions) is created.

The head of the CSG is approved by the administrative bodies. He will be the Senior Coach's Deputy for Scientific and Methodological Support, with whom he

will be responsible for team preparation. The CSG includes specialists in pedagogy, psychology and medical biology.

The responsibilities of a CSG specialist with a senior coach include:

- prediction of model descriptions and sports achievements, stage-by-stage norms of training of players' training and competition activities;
- training and strategy of the game on the field;
- development of targeted programs for the preparation for major competitions;
- development of recommendations for the rational combination of competition and training loads with various restorative means and their implementation in practice;
- analysis of plan implementation indicators;
- processing the results of inspections and presenting them to the coach and higher authorities;
- promoting scientific knowledge among coaches and athletes.

Medical-biological specialists monitor the working skills of handball players and conduct in-depth medical examinations.

The basis of scientific and methodological support is modern scientific research on the most pressing problems of handball.

At this stage in the development of handball, research is of particular importance. In all major international competitions - in the struggle for the title of "strongest in the world" in the fierce battles of many rivals, there is hope to generalize the experience of sports practice without objectively determining the quantitative and qualitative changes in the activities of handball teams. will not lip. It is impossible to effectively plan and manage training and competition activities without an objective assessment of the dynamics of the athlete's physical abilities, changes in the state of functional systems in his body, the level of all types of training.

Sport is a creative process that requires knowledge and experience, as well as specific scientific training. The level of achievement of the specialist and his / her dissatisfaction with the theoretical recommendations in the field of his / her practical activity should create the need for scientific research.

A prerequisite for conducting research is its practical value. Before embarking on research, it is important to master the theoretical foundations and practical skills of the chosen sport, to gain in-depth knowledge.

Getting acquainted with the historical, theoretical and practical aspects of the research topic should be comprehensive, based on the study of methodological literature and analysis of practical activities. After that, the main directions of research, the working hypothesis are determined, the organizational forms of work and specific methods are clarified. A work plan is currently being developed.

A set of different research methods from a number of interrelated disciplines (psychology, physiology, biochemistry, etc.) and a group of pedagogical methods specific to handball are used to study different aspects of handball.

Experimental research (laboratory, model and natural experiments) is the basis of scientific work, which allows you to objectively demonstrate the impact of this or that factor, training methodology in a specially organized environment, determine the degree of its impact on the athlete's body, etc.

The analysis of the obtained data is a necessary part of any scientific research, on the basis of which conclusions are made and recommendations for practical application are given.

The results of the work can be announced, presented at conferences, symposia, seminars for coaches and researchers, and presented in lectures for handball players.

Analysis of sports training documents (diaries of cadets and trainees, individual work plans, team training plans, competition protocols, etc.), interviews with coaches, handball players, researchers in order to study practical work experience possible. It is advisable to use special questionnaires to get the opinion of experts on a problem in a particular field of research (in the questionnaire the answers are given in the form of “yes” or “no”). However, it should be borne in mind that the answers to the questionnaire are not the decisive criterion for assessing this or that event. The basis of scientific research is practice and facts.

A pedagogical examination is a record of individual performance of a handball player made up of cadets and listeners without the researcher being deeply involved in the activity. Pedagogical observation is based on objective methods, such as photographs, videos, and so on.

Experiment is a method of scientific research in which the events and conditions of interest to the researcher are deliberately created by him. Experiments can be divided into natural, model, or laboratory types, depending on the circumstances.

The natural experience takes place in the normal activities of both the trainee and the trainee. For example, a pulse during a game can be detected by radiotelemetry without affecting the progress of the game and without interfering with the player.

In a model experiment, the conditions of interest to the researcher are created, and the influence of one of the factors that is consciously changed on the outcome of the study and training of the trainee and the listener is determined. For example, the use of a trainer or a specific intensity program in training.

In a laboratory experiment, conditions are created that are far removed from the practice of the practice in order to eliminate the adjoining factors that may affect the results of the experiment.

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The pedagogical practice provides for specially organized sessions with the experimental and control groups of the subjects on the basis of the developed plan.

These groups should be homogeneous in composition, with no difference in gender, age, qualifications, or health status. The results of the research on the experimental and control groups are compared with each other and with the initial data, and conclusions are drawn about the effectiveness of this or that training methodology.

Scientific work is traditionally described in the following order:

1. An introductory part justifying the relevance of the chosen topic.
2. The review of the literature provides an in-depth analysis of the state of the research on the selected topic.
3. Tasks, methods and organization of research.
4. Discussion of research results.
5. Conclusions and methodical recommendations for practical application. The diploma work of the cadet and the trainee is a type of scientific work based on personal scientific experience or control research.

The dissertation for a degree is a scientific work on a topic, in which the problem is studied, the methodology of the experiment, its organization, course and results, the conclusions drawn on the basis of a comprehensive analysis of experimental data and its application in practice. The methodological recommendations for are described in detail.

The scientific work is published in the form of a dissertation, scientific article, abstract, monograph, methodical article, textbook or manual.

A scientific article is a summary of the problem, the content of the scientific work, the course of the scientific experiment, the analysis of the data obtained, and the conclusions.

The abstract summarizes the essence of the work.

The methodological article is a public presentation of the main conclusions and recommendations on teaching and learning methods in order to put them into practice.

The monograph is the culmination of many years of research by the author and his readers.

A textbook or study guide is a generalized statement of conclusions and recommendations that emerges from a series of scientific studies and outlines pedagogical ways to apply them in practice.

Information is an important factor in the development of handball. At this stage of the game's development, the main areas of information gathering are:

1. Development trends of world handball. There is a need to monitor the trends in the organization of children's sports - youth sports and skilled sports, club management and financing of handball.
2. Scientific and methodological information, the latest scientific developments.
3. Summarize the practical experience of the competition and training process.

Conferences, scientific collections, journals, dissertations, abstracts, articles on the Internet, pedagogical observations, newspaper articles, interviews with coaches, experts, athletes can serve as sources for gathering information.

CONCLUSION

Unfortunately, the information supply of handball in Uzbekistan is not so good. Television coverage of competitions is limited, the amount of work published in the press is very low, the scientific work on the theory and methodology of handball is the same, and the process of training coaches is not organized. All this is reflected in the development of handball in Uzbekistan.

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